

FREQUENCY OF SURGICAL SITE INFECTION AND ANTIMICROBIAL SENSITIVITY PATTERN OF BACTERIAS ISOLATED IN ABDOMINAL SURGERIES IN OBSTETRICS AND GYNAE POPULATION

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Abstract

Objective: This study aims to evaluate the frequency of surgical site infections, to determine the antimicrobial sensitivity pattern of microbial pathogens isolated in abdominal surgeries in the obstetrics and gynecology department post-surgery, and to study the predictors and risk factors of SSIs.

Methods: This is a prospective cross-sectional study. The approval for the study was taken from the IRB of Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Center Karachi. A total no of patients who had undergone abdominal surgical procedures (laparotomy, Caesarean section, also termed as C-section, and abdominal hysterectomy) were included in this study. The outpatient or ambulatory were excluded. Vaginal, laproscopic and minimal incision surgeries (tube ligation), were not included in the study. The frequencies were measure through SPSS 27.

Results: We have observed 1304 procedures, of them emergency caesarian sections were 1151, elective CS were 51, 38 hysterectomies and laparotomies 64. The SSI was reported in 225 (17.2%) patients. The data was taken from patients who had developed SSI. Among culture-positive samples, methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) was isolated in 42 cases (18.9%), *Escherichia coli* in 33 cases (14.9%), *Pseudomonas* species in 30 cases (13.5%), *Acinetobacter* species in 18 cases (8.1%), *Klebsiella oxytoca* in 9 cases (4.1%), *Proteus* species in 6 cases (2.7%), *Staphylococcus aureus* in 3 cases (1.4%), and *Moraxella morganii* in 3 cases (1.4%).

Conclusion: In conclusion, this study emphasizes that SSIs remain a significant postoperative complication, particularly following emergency procedures. The predominance of multidrug-resistant organisms reinforces the need for robust infection control practices, rational antibiotic use, and regular surveillance of local antimicrobial resistance patterns.

INTRODUCTION

Surgical site infections are the most prevalent reason for HAI after urinary tract infection (1). SSI per CDC guidelines is defined as any infection

involving the surgical site after 30 days of procedure or within 90 days if an implant or prosthesis is in situ (2). They are caused by penetration of the surgical site by endogenous and

/or exogenous microbes during the surgery (primary infection) and after surgery (secondary infection) (3, 4). Primary infection occurs within 5-7 days of surgery and is more harmful (5). The prevalence of HAI'S in Southeast Asia was 9 % with a pooled incidence of SSI of 7.8%, while the prevalence in Pakistan ranged up to 33.6% (6, 7). Risk factors include prolonged surgery, patient age, prolonged hospitalization, comorbidities, malnutrition, and the surgical site (8). It also includes prolonged urinary catheterization, malignant lesions, repeated vaginal examinations, and intraoperative bleeding > 300 ml (9).

SSI is leading to disability, prolonged hospitalization, which ultimately causes antimicrobial resistance by increased use of antibiotics (10). Re-hospitalization healthcare expenses, drug and diagnostics costs, and utilization increases (11). The management of SSI is now challenging due to an increase drug resistant microorganism (12).

Surgical site infections (SSIs) remain a source of threat and pose postoperative complications, morbidity, and substantial values of post-surgical mortalities. Early researchers linked anaerobic microflora to surgical infection and helped pave the road for significant improvements in patient treatment with antibiotics, both preventative and curative

Subsequent research has focused on identifying risk variables and forecasting postoperative infection rates (13). Appropriate procedures need to be carried out to manage the high rate of infection by all accessible methods, as antibiotics alone may not be adequate to prevail in this battle. In previous studies, numerous preventable causes of SSI have been recognized and documented for proper implementation to reduce the incidence of such infections, but infection does occur. As the progression and development of SSI is a process of complex nature, which is mainly reliant on more than a few dissimilar factors associated with the patient, involvement of staff, the atmosphere and instrumentation of the surgical facility, and lastly, the technique of surgery. This study was designed to identify the areas that need to be addressed with respect to the risk factors for future reduction in the incidence of SSI in our population.

This study aims to evaluate the frequency of surgical site infections, to determine the antimicrobial sensitivity pattern of microbial pathogens isolated in abdominal surgeries in the obstetrics and gynecology department post-surgery, and to study the predictors and risk factors of SSIs.

MATERIAL AND METHODS:

This is a prospective cross-sectional study. The participants were selected through a convenience sampling technique from the Obstetrics and Gynecology Department of Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Center Karachi. The approval for the study was taken from the IRB of Jinnah Postgraduate Medical Center Karachi . All individuals were informed about the study methods, purpose, procedure, adverse effects, and that the data would be published anonymously. Patients have provided written informed consent for their participation in the research, and all protocols of declarations of Helsinki were adopted throughout the study.

A total no of patients who had undergone abdominal surgical procedures (laparotomy, Caesarean section, also termed as C-section, and abdominal hysterectomy) were included in this study.

All Primary incisional SSIs (superficial/deep) noticed through different surveillance mechanism (admissions, re-admissions, and post hospital discharge surveillance) after major obstetrical and gynecological abdominal surgeries were included. The outpatient or ambulatory were excluded. Vaginal, laproscopic and minimal incision surgeries (tube ligation), were not included in the study.

SSI is characterized as, infection occurs within 30 days after the operation, and infection involves the skin or subcutaneous tissue of the incision with at least one of the signs and symptoms (Pain (VAS >3), Redness, swelling at the site of the incision, Fever with a temperature of more than 100.4 F, Purilin discharge from the suture site of the infection), All these signs and symptoms were assessed clinically.

All factors were categorized, leading to an SSI. A preliminary list of essential events was formulated

depending on the most important risk factors documented in the existing literature for SSIs and noted on pre designed proforma. The patients were followed up in OPD after 1 week after discharge and then at the end of the 4th week for SSI. The final outcome of SSI was measured at 28th day by the researcher, and SSI was labeled as positive as per the operational definition. All this relevant information was recorded in a proforma. The minimum sample size required for the study is 131. The expected frequency of SSI is 9.4% (13). The power of study is 80, and margin of error is 5%. NCSS PASS helped in calculation of sample size.

The proforma was filled during the interview of the patient at the baseline. The base line variables (Age, BMI, Comorbidities, Anemia, ASA,

Preoperative transfusion, surgery type (elective/emergency), pre-operative antibiotic, and Procedure). Post-operatively MRSA infection and wound type were noted.

Data was evaluated with a descriptive statistical approach. SPSS (27) software used for statistical evaluation. The categorical variables are expressed in frequencies and percentages.

Results:

In the six months, we have observed 1304 procedures, of them emergency caesarian sections were 1151, elective CS were 51, 38 hysterectomies and laparotomies 64. The SSI was reported in 225 (17.2%) patients. The data was taken from patients who had developed SSI.

Age (years)	18-25	69 (30.7)
	25+ - 35	129 (57.3)
	35+ - 45	18 (8)
	45+ - 60	9 (4)
	>60	9 (4)
BMI (kg/m ²)	<18.5	9 (4.1)
	18.5 - 24.9	141 (64.4)
	25 - 29.9	60 (27.4)
	>30	9 (4.1)
Comorbidities	yes	57 (25.3)
	No	168 (74.7)
Diabetes	yes	54 (24)
	No	171 (76)
Hypertension	yes	57 (25.3)
	No	168 (74.7)
Anemia	yes	54 (24)
	No	171 (76)
Others	yes	45 (20)
	No	180 (80)
Hospital stay Days	2 or less than 2 days	183 (81.3)
	>2 days	42 (18.7)
Postoperative Days	7 or less than 7 days	60 (26.7)
	8 to 14 days	102 (45.3)
	15 or >15 days	63 (28)
Surgical Characteristics		
Type of surgery	elective	39 (17.3)
	emergency	186 (82.7)
Procedure	cesarean section	186 (82.7)
	hysterectomy	27 (12)

	laparotomy	12 (5.3)
Duration of surgery	< 1hr	180 (80)
	> 1hr	45 (20)

The majority, 129 patients (57.3%), belonged to the 25 to 35 years age group. Body mass index (BMI) assessment showed 141 patients (64.4%) had a BMI between 18.5 and 24.9 kg/m². Overall comorbidities were present in 57 patients (25.3%). Diabetes mellitus was identified in 54 patients (24.0%). Hypertension was present in 57 patients (25.3%). Anemia was reported in 54 patients (24.0%). The duration of hospital stay was two days or less in 183 patients (81.3%). Post-procedure follow-up duration was between 8 and 14 days in 102 patients (45.3%), (Table 1).

Emergency surgeries accounted for 186 cases (82.7%). Regarding the type of surgical procedure,

cesarean section was the most common, performed in 186 patients (82.7%). The duration of surgery was less than one hour in 180 patients (80.0%). Preoperative antibiotic prophylaxis was administered to 105 patients (46.7%). Among those who received prophylaxis, ceftriaxone was used in all cases (table 1).

Superficial SSI was identified in 69 patients (32.4%). Redness was observed in 102 patients (66.7%). Pain was present in 207 patients (92%). Swelling was noted in 69 patients (56.1%). Discharge from the wound was present in 207 patients (92%). Fever was reported in 123 patients (69.5%).

Table 2: Surgical Site Infection Characteristics

SSI type	superficial	69 (32.4)
	deep	144 (67.6)
SSI symptoms	YES	213 (94.7)
	No	12 (5.3)
REDNESS	YES	102 (47.8)
PAIN	YES	207 (97.2)
SWELLING	YES	69 (32.4)
DISCHARGE	YES	207 (97.2)
FEVER	YES	123 (57.7)
Other symptoms	YES	6 (3)

Wound cultures were obtained from 219 patients (98.6%). No microbial growth was detected in 78 cases (35.1%). Among culture-positive samples, methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus* (MRSA) was isolated in 42 cases (18.9%), *Escherichia coli* in 33 cases (14.9%), *Pseudomonas*

species in 30 cases (13.5%), *Acinetobacter* species in 18 cases (8.1%), *Klebsiella oxytoca* in 9 cases (4.1%), *Proteus* species in 6 cases (2.7%), *Staphylococcus aureus* in 3 cases (1.4%), and *Moraxella morgani* in 3 cases (1.4%).

Table 3: Microbiological Findings

Culture taken from SSI	yes	219 (98.6)
	No	3 (1.4)
Organism isolated	NO GROWTH	78 (35.1)
	MRSA	42 (18.9)
	ECOLI	33 (14.9)
	PSEUDOMONAS	30 (13.5)

ACINOBACTER	18 (8.1)
KLEBSIELA OXYTOCA	9 (4.1)
STAPH AUREUS	3 (1.4)
PROTEUS	6 (2.7)
GRAM +VE COCCI	0 (0)
MOREXALLA MORGANII	3 (1.4)

Antibiotic sensitivity testing was performed in 147 cases (65.3%). Sensitivity to amoxicillin-clavulanic acid was seen in 12 cases (5.3%), ceftriaxone in 9 cases (4.0%), ciprofloxacin in 6 cases (2.7%), gentamicin in 72 cases (32.0%), vancomycin in 18 cases (8.0%), and linezolid in 18 cases (8.0%). Sensitivity to other antibiotics was observed in 48 cases (21.3%). Higher sensitivity was noted for meropenem in 114 cases (50.7%), followed by tazobactam in 39 cases (17.3%), colistin in 36 cases (16.0%), minocycline in 36 cases (16.0%), tigecycline in 12 cases (5.3%), and clindamycin in 15 cases (6.7%).

Resistance patterns revealed high resistance rates to amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, ceftriaxone, and ciprofloxacin, each observed in 138 cases (61.3%). Resistance to metronidazole was noted in 141 cases (62.7%), while resistance to gentamicin was present in 27 cases (12.0%). Vancomycin resistance was observed in 45 cases (20.0%), and linezolid resistance in 12 cases (5.3%).

Re-operation was required in 27 patients (12.0%). The final outcome was favorable in all cases, with complete recovery observed in 225 patients (100.0%). There were no cases of re-hospitalization or complications.

Table 4: Antibiotic Sensitivity and Resistance Patterns, Treatment and Outcomes n (%):

Sensitivity test	yes	147 (65.3)	
	No	78 (34.7)	
		Sensitivity	Resistance
Amoxicillin clavulanic acid	yes	12 (5.3)	138 (61.3)
Ceftriaxone Sensitivity	yes	9 (4)	138 (61.3)
Ciprofloxacin Sensitivity	yes	6 (2.7)	138 (61.3)
Gentamycin Sensitivity	yes	72 (32)	27 (12)
Metronidazole Sensitivity	yes	0 (0)	141 (62.7)
Vancomycin Sensitivity	yes	18 (8)	45 (20)
Linezolid Sensitivity	yes	18 (8)	12 (5.3)
Other Sensitivity	yes	48 (21.3)	3 (1.3)
Meropenem Sensitivity	yes	114 (50.7)	
Colistin Sensitivity	yes	36 (16)	
Minocycline Sensitivity	yes	36 (16)	
Tazobactum Sensitivity	yes	39 (17.3)	
tigecycline Sensitivity	yes	12 (5.3)	
Clindamycin Sensitivity	yes	15 (6.7)	
Treatment and Outcomes			
Treatment	yes	225 (100)	
	No	0 (0)	
Reoperation	yes	27 (12)	
	No	198 (88)	
Final outcome	recovered	225 (100)	
	Re hospitalized	0 (0)	

	complication	0 (0)	
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DISCUSSION

This study provides a comprehensive overview of the demographic profile, clinical characteristics, microbiological spectrum, antimicrobial susceptibility patterns, and outcomes of patients with surgical site infections (SSIs) following predominantly emergency obstetric and gynecological procedures. The affected population largely comprised young adults, most of whom had a normal body mass index, with a substantial proportion having underlying comorbidities such as diabetes, hypertension, and anemia.

Emergency surgeries, particularly cesarean sections, accounted for the majority of procedures associated with SSI. Deep surgical site infections were more frequent than superficial infections, and all patients presented with clinical symptoms, most commonly pain, wound discharge, fever, and redness. In our study, Microbiological analysis demonstrated a heterogeneous spectrum of pathogens, with methicillin-resistant *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas*, and *Acinetobacter* species being the most frequently isolated organisms, while a notable proportion of cultures showed no growth. The growing impact of antibiotic-resistant bacteria within the context of surgical site infections poses a major challenge to modern surgical care. Research by Munawar et al. describes a diverse bacterial environment, identifying *Staphylococcus aureus* (16.2%) and coagulase-negative staphylococci (CoNS) as the primary Gram-positive organisms, while *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* (11.5%), *Klebsiella pneumoniae* (9.09%), *Escherichia coli* (13.8%), and *Acinetobacter* spp. (11.6%) represent the most common Gram-negative isolates (7)[26]. The high frequency of *S. aureus* is largely attributed to its role as a common skin inhabitant, which enables it to colonize surgical wounds readily, though the hospital environment and unclean surgical tools remain significant external sources (14).

Supporting data from Ali et al. reflect these findings, documenting *S. aureus* (66.7%) and CoNS (19.05%) as the leading Gram-positive agents, while *E. coli* (33.3%) and *K. pneumoniae*

(25%) appear as the most frequent Gram-negative pathogens (7)[24]. Systematic reviews and multicenter studies, specifically those by Singh et al., indicate that Gram-negative strains often exceed Gram-positive bacteria in postoperative wound infections, accounting for 56.25% and 43.75%, respectively (15-17)[29, 30]. This trend is further confirmed by evidence from Sierra Leone and Ethiopia, where Gram-negative organisms made up between 80% and 83% of the total bacterial isolates (18, 19)[8, 11].

In our study, antimicrobial susceptibility testing demonstrated high levels of resistance to commonly used antibiotics, including ceftriaxone, ciprofloxacin, and amoxicillin-clavulanic acid, whereas relatively higher sensitivity was observed with carbapenems and selected reserve antibiotics. These findings highlight the growing challenge of antimicrobial resistance in SSIs and underscore the importance of culture-guided therapy.

In our study, the frequency of SSI is 17.2%. The clinical frequency of SSIs shows significant variation, depending on geographic locations, hospital cleaning protocols, and surgical skill. While research in Northeast Ethiopia reports clinical infection rates of 14.5%, much lower rates have been recorded in Addis Ababa (9.8%) and Alexandria, Egypt (2.3%) (13, 20). On the other hand, higher rates found in regions such as Harari and Mekelle highlight those clinical habits and the strictness of preventive measures are essential to lowering infection risks (19, 21-24). Such differences often relate to the presence of advanced medical infrastructure including high-quality air filtration and standard sterilization methods which may be lacking in poorly funded healthcare settings (13).

S. aureus remains the main isolate in obstetric procedures like cesarean sections, a finding consistent with regional data from Uganda and Nigeria (13).

Analysis of antibiotic sensitivity patterns highlights a worrying trend of reduced effectiveness among standard treatments. Enterobacteriaceae isolates show very high resistance to ampicillin (91.3%), augmentin

(87%), and ceftriaxone (78.3%) (13). This resistance is likely made worse by the common use of these drugs for prevention before surgery. Notably, the presence of multidrug-resistant (MDR) types is remarkably high; a previous study identified MDR rates of 88.9% for Gram-negative and 66.7% for Gram-positive isolates. Although these figures differ from findings in Egypt (13%), the overall trend emphasizes a global health crisis caused by poor sensitivity testing, unnecessary antibiotic use, and long hospital stays (13, 20). Accurate description of these resistant groups is necessary for the creation of careful antibiotic management plans and the improvement of patient recovery after surgery.

Despite the burden of infection and antimicrobial resistance, clinical outcomes were favorable, with all patients achieving recovery. Reoperation was required in a minority of cases, and most patients had a short hospital stay, reflecting effective clinical management and timely intervention.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this study emphasizes that SSIs remain a significant postoperative complication, particularly following emergency procedures. The predominance of multidrug-resistant organisms reinforces the need for robust infection control practices, rational antibiotic use, and regular surveillance of local antimicrobial resistance patterns. These measures are essential to optimize patient outcomes, reduce healthcare burden, and guide evidence-based surgical and antimicrobial stewardship policies.

The study highlights SSIs as a significant postoperative complication, particularly following emergency procedures. Strengthening infection prevention strategies, optimizing perioperative antibiotic use, and maintaining continuous surveillance of local resistance patterns are essential to reduce SSI-related morbidity and improve patient care.

Strengths and Limitations

A key strength of this study lies in its comprehensive assessment of clinical presentation, microbiological profile, antimicrobial susceptibility, and patient outcomes,

providing a holistic overview of SSIs in a real-world clinical setting. The high rate of culture sampling enhances the reliability of the microbiological findings, and complete follow-up data allowed for accurate assessment of short-term outcomes.

However, several limitations should be acknowledged. The single-center design may limit the generalizability of the findings to other healthcare settings with differing surgical practices or antimicrobial policies. The observational nature of the study precludes causal inference, and potential confounding factors could not be fully controlled. Additionally, long-term outcomes and recurrence rates were not evaluated, and molecular characterization of resistant organisms was not performed.

Despite these limitations, the study offers valuable insights into the current epidemiology and management of SSIs and provides clinically relevant data to inform antimicrobial stewardship and infection control strategies.

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